

Simultaneous Recording of Otoacoustic Emissions and Envelope-Following Responses to Evaluate Efferent Influences on Neural Coding

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Abstract. Antimasking effects of the medial olivocochlear (MOC) efferent system using a chinchilla animal model were explored. Envelope following responses (EFRs) and transient evoked otoacoustic emissions (TEOAEs) were measured in an interleaved manner to assess the response under forward-masking conditions with a 40-dB noise level compared to unmasked conditions. A computational model incorporating the MOC efferent system was used to develop hypotheses and design the experiment. Preliminary results show an increase in EFR in normal-hearing chinchillas with forward masking, which was diminished in carboplatin exposure chinchillas (inner-hair-cell damage in chinchilla). In addition, for the stimuli with modulation frequencies higher than the typical range of the modulation transfer functions (MTF) of inferior colliculus (IC) cells the enhancement was less strong (as predicted by the model). TEOAEs demonstrated a decrease in gain during the noise masker and stimuli with modulation frequencies within the MTF range, and less gain reduction with higher modulation frequencies outside the MTF. This study supports the hypothesis that MOC activity is involved in the antimasking effect observed in forward masking and this effect is dependent on modulation frequency due to the IC input to MOC.

INTRODUCTION

The medial olivocochlear (MOC) efferent system potentially plays a significant role in neural coding and perception, but it is less explored compared to the ascending auditory pathway. One of the challenges in studying MOC efferent system is the absence of a standard measurement for measuring the system's activity. Psychophysical studies have been introduced to measure MOC efferent effect [1] and have been beneficial in gaining mechanistic insights into the MOC efferent system. However, it remains uncertain whether the observed effect can be solely attributed to the MOC efferent system. Otoacoustic emissions (OAEs) have also been used for assessing MOC efferent activity [2], however, despite their extensive use, there have been controversial results arising from the different methodologies used in measuring OAEs. Different acoustic stimuli used in measuring OAEs can lead to varying assessments of MOC activity and in some of these measurements, the acoustic stimuli can activate the efferent system itself and result in confounding results. Previously, most studies using OAEs as a measure for efferent activity didn't focus on the role of midbrain modulation-sensitive input to the MOC. However, anatomical studies show a significant projection from the inferior colliculus (IC) to MOC cells [3]. Given that IC cells are sensitive to low-frequency modulations, design of the stimuli should consider this effect [4].

One of the most critical unanswered questions about the efferent system that is still under debate is the role of the MOC system [5-7]. Antimasking has been suggested as one of the roles for the efferent system in previous studies [8]. Recent studies also shows that while listening to a signal, exposure to mild noise (40-60 dB SPL) can lead to increased envelope-following responses (EFRs) and improved modulation detection [9,10]. This enhancement could be a result

of an increase in effective modulation depth following the efferent activity [11]. We studied this effect in EFR response in a chinchilla animal model to study the effect of anesthesia and selective types of hearing loss, comparing these results with those from human studies, to understand the source of contributors to this effect. Animal studies are valuable for gaining insights into the different pathways of the MOC efferent system and their underlying mechanisms, particularly by using animal models with specific, well-characterized hearing loss pathologies. The MOC neurons receive two major excitatory projections from auditory periphery from the IC and the cochlear nucleus (CN). Projections from CN is from the cell types that have wide-dynamic-range (WDR), including T-stellate cells (Blackburn and Sachs, 1990; Guinan, 2018; Romero & Trussell, 2021) and neurons in the small cell cap that receive inputs from L/MSR AN fibers (Ye et al., 2000; Fekete et al., 1984). Projections from IC cells contribute to the modulation transfer functions (MTFs) of MOC neurons [3,13], suggesting IC cells with band-enhanced MTF project to MOC. Considering the sensitivity of IC cells to low-frequency modulation, the stimulus modulation frequency could influence efferent activity. This hypothesis is tested through a comparison of responses to stimuli with modulation frequencies within and outside the typical MTF range of IC cells.

A subcortical auditory model incorporating MOC efferent dynamic gain control system with inputs from the auditory brainstem and midbrain [11,12] was used to optimally design these physiological experiments and interpret the resulting data. Our computational modeling (Fig. 1) suggests that during the noise masker, the cochlear gain decreases (Fig. 1-F) due to the strong IC input (Fig. 1-D) to the MOC in response to the wideband noise, as fluctuations in the noise fall within the range of the MTF. The CN input, modeled with low spontaneous rate (LSR) response (L/MSR) to the MOC, is not very strong (Fig. 1-B) in response to the noise masker because the sound level is low. During the SAM tone, the IC rate is strongly affected by modulation frequency. For modulation frequencies within the range of the MTF, the gain continues to decrease (Fig. 1-F, top) due to the strong IC rates (Fig. 1-D, right panel), which input to the MOC. For the SAM tone with the modulation frequency that is outside the range of the MTF, the gain is recovering (Fig. 1-F, bottom), reducing the difference in gain for forward masking relative to unmasked conditions. This in turn can decrease the modulation depth and decrease the modulation enhancement effect making it less dominant for out-of-MTF conditions. Using this model, we also simulated the evoked potential calculated based on the sum of AN and IC responses across CFs (Fig. 1-E). The simulated population response also

FIGURE 1. Model with MOC [11]. A) Forward masking stimulus with modulation frequency of 303 Hz (left) and 103 Hz (right) B) LSR AN fiber, C) HSR AN fiber response and D) IC neuron responses on CF stimuli. E) simulated evoked potential response. F) Cochlear outer-hair-cell gain, due to fluctuations in the masker and 103 Hz-modulated tone, was reduced over time, but not for the modulated tone with modulation frequency of 303 Hz (outside the IC MTF).

shows an increased response in forward masking conditions compared to the unmasked condition for 103 Hz (Fig. 1-E, right), but it is not increasing the response for the 303 Hz condition (Fig. 1-E, left).

To investigate the impact of MOC activity on neural coding, we have recorded interleaved OAEs and EFRs to track the correlation between the change in cochlear gain and neural coding during acoustic stimulation. We then test whether chinchillas with selective inner-hair-cell damage due to carboplatin show effects on the EFRs and OAEs. Carboplatin-induced selective inner hair cell (IHC) loss can impact the efferent system by decreasing the input to the MOC via the brainstem. Our initial findings show less modulation enhancement in carboplatin exposed chinchillas compared to normal hearing group, potentially indicating reduced efferent effect.

METHODS

Stimuli: The stimulus (Fig. 2.A) is a forward masking paradigm with a 500 ms noise masker (100 Hz to 10,000 Hz). The target, appearing 50 ms after the masker, is a 300 ms sinusoidally amplitude-modulated (SAM) tone with a 2000 Hz carrier frequency and a modulation frequency of either 103 Hz (within MTF range) or 303 Hz (outside MTF range). The SAM sound level is 80 dB SPL, and the Gaussian noise level is 40 dB SPL. Responses are averaged over 200 total repetitions with alternating phase.

FIGURE 2. A) Stimulus for interleaved recording of EFRs and TEOAEs. B) Raw TEOAE responses to the clicks.

Subjects: Three chinchillas with normal hearing and two chinchillas exposed to carboplatin were used. For the carboplatin exposure, chinchillas received an intraperitoneal injection of 38 mg/kg of carboplatin. Post-injection, animals were monitored closely for 10 days, receiving 10 cc of lactated Ringer's solution subcutaneously daily. Our carboplatin exposure paradigm in chinchillas results in 10-15% IHC loss across the cochlea without any OHC loss [14]. Prior studies using scanning electron microscopy show IHC stereocilia damage following carboplatin exposure in the IHCs that remain [14, 15].

Procedure and Analysis: Interleaved measurements of transient evoked otoacoustic emissions (TEOAEs) and EFRs in a forward masking paradigm were recorded in awake chinchillas restrained comfortably using our successful awake-restraint procedure [16]. Simultaneous measurement is crucial to ensure consistent conditions and account for cortical or attention effects that could influence both measurements by altering cortical inputs to MOC and efferent activity [2,3]. Three clicks will be presented: 25 ms before (Fig. 2.B, black) and after the masker (Fig.2.B, red), and 25 ms after the target (Fig.2.B, blue). For TEOAE analysis, data from positive polarity clicks and negative polarity clicks were analyzed separately and compared. Using the clicks to measure change in TEOAEs before and after the stimuli was inspired by Feld et al, 2024 [17] and the method for analyzing the TEOAEs responses followed Goodman et al. (2021) [18]. The time analysis window was determined by comparing the click response in an infinite tube and in-ear. Subsequently, a band-pass filter (850 Hz to 8 kHz) was applied, responses were ramped, and artifacts were rejected based on RMS values and outlier detection. The response was then processed through a 64-filter bank, and a frequency-specific time window was applied to the output of each filter. Finally, the SNR for each frequency was calculated and evaluated separately. EFRs were collected using subdermal electrodes with 200 repetitions of alternating phase stimuli. The response envelope was analyzed by averaging over positive and negative polarity repetitions. The spectral analysis was performed by calculating the phase locking value (PLV) to measure the consistency of the phase across individual trials' responses at each frequency [19]. Physiological measures were collected using a Tucker-Davis Technology system with our publicly available software [20].

RESULTS

EFR Response in the Normal Hearing Group and Effect of Modulation Frequency

The phase locking value (PLV) was computed from the EFR responses ($n=3$; animals awake; Fig.3.A). Increase in EFR response for forward masking condition (Fig. 3.B) is consistent with observations from human listeners [9]. This enhancement was most notable at the first EFR harmonic across subjects, with a more pronounced effect observed at the 103 Hz modulation frequency than at 303 Hz. This suggests a frequency-dependent enhancement of the EFR aligned with known properties of the MOC system.

FIGURE 3. A) PLV of EFR neural response and time domain response (top window) in awake animal. B) change in neural response with MOC activity comparison for 103 and 303 Hz stimuli

Effect of Carboplatin Exposure

The modulation enhancements based on the first three harmonics of PLV from EFR responses were calculated and compared between normal hearing ($n=3$; animals awake) and carboplatin-exposed animals ($n=3$; animals awake) (Fig. 3). A clear modulation enhancement was observed in all normal hearing chinchillas at 103 Hz, but this enhancement was reduced at 303 Hz. In the carboplatin-exposed group, no enhancement was evident at 103 Hz. However, intriguingly, the trend reversed from 103 Hz to 303 Hz, with one of the carboplatin-exposed chinchillas showing an unexpected slight enhancement at the higher modulation frequency. This alteration in response pattern post-carboplatin exposure suggests a potential disruption in the auditory system such as a broadening of modulation filters. The modulation enhancement calculated as described in Eq. 1, where $P_{i,FW}$ is the i^{th} PLV harmonic of the response to the stimulus following the forward masker and $P_{i,S}$ is the i^{th} PLV harmonic of the unmasked stimulus response.

$$\text{Modulation Enhancement} = 20 \times \log_{10} \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 P_{i,FW}}{\sum_{i=1}^3 P_{i,S}} \right) \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 4. Comparison of modulation enhancement based on first three harmonics in EFR PLV of the EFR responses between normal hearing (left) and carboplatin exposed (right) animals.

TEOAEs Recorded Interleaved with EFR

TEOAEs were recorded interleaved with the EFR to assess the effect of the masker and signal on the efferent activity. These measurements aligned with the EFR findings. To study the robustness of TEOAE measurements, responses between positive and negative clicks were analyzed separately and compared. Results for one chinchilla for which the response had a good SNR (at 60 dB peSPL click level, Fig. 5) shows a wide frequency decrease affected by masker compared to the silence response, where the difference before and after the click is around zero (Fig 5B). For the SAM tone, a decrease in response at the carrier frequency is observed, but much more pronounced for the 103 Hz stimulus compared to 303 Hz (Fig 5A), which aligns with our hypothesis. Results are generally consistent across other animals, but with large variability in SNR. This motivates determining the optimal click level for each animal prior by finding the loudest click (highest SNR) for which the clicks in isolation do not induce efferent effects in future studies to optimize stimulus conditions.

FIGURE 5. TEOAEs changed in response to A) SAM with 103 (black) and 303 Hz (red) modulation frequency; B) masker (red), silence (black, control),

Discussion

Increased EFR responses were observed following a mild forward-masking noise in awake normal-hearing chinchillas. The enhancement decreases with carboplatin exposure, anesthesia, and higher modulation frequencies outside the IC MTF. The MOC efferent system is suggested as one potential contributor to this observation. The computational model suggests that modulation-frequency dependency of the enhancement effect likely results from reduced input from the IC to the MOC as the modulation frequency is out of the band of the MTF, resulting in reduced MOC drive and thus cochlear gain recovery. The simultaneous measurements of TEOAEs indicate a more dominant gain reduction at modulation frequencies within MTF range of IC, specifically at 103 Hz, compared to higher frequencies such as 303 Hz. This suggests that the MOC activity decreases as the modulation frequency increases beyond the peak sensitivity of the MTF. Future studies are needed to optimize the click level and subsequent analysis of TEOAEs by accounting for species-specific and subject-specific properties. Furthermore, investigating the effects of noise and signal levels with additional data collection could provide deeper insights.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Vaclav Vencovsky: Dear authors, interesting results. I have a few questions. People with hearing loss have often difficulties recognizing speech in noise. Why the cochlear gain reduction due to the MOC reflex help normal hearing people, but cochlear gain reduction due to hearing loss has the opposite effect? In Fig. 5, you point to the cases where we see a reduction of TEOAE amplitude but omit that in Fig. 5B the TEOAE amplitude around 1.3 kHz increased after the target by the same amount as it decreased in the cases you point to. Does the frequency selectivity of the cochlea determine the MTF in IC? You use sinusoids with two modulation frequencies (103 and 303 Hz) and a carrier of 2 kHz. At 2 kHz, the two side bands 300 Hz apart from 2 kHz carrier will be resolved but 100 Hz apart side bands not. How does the TEOAE phase differ in these conditions?

Afagh Farhadi: Thank you for your insightful comments. Regarding the effects of hearing loss, studies have shown that individuals with hearing loss can sometimes perform better in certain conditions for amplitude modulation (AM) detection, which aligns with our hypothesis. However, the difficulties in hearing in noise may stem from the fact that hearing loss does not dynamically adjust cochlear gain based on the input sound, instead leading to a general decrease in gain across all frequencies. In contrast, the MOC efferent system can dynamically and frequency-specifically modulate gain based on input level (via CN input) and spectral information (via IC input).

Concerning the TEOAE results, we acknowledge that the previous figures were noisy and made it difficult to observe the effects clearly. We have improved our analysis methods and figure representations, which now allow the modulation frequency effects to be seen more reliably (Fig. 5). As for your question about resolved and unresolved sidebands, we agree that further investigation into this effect, particularly in chinchillas, is necessary to understand how it might influence our results. The differences in TEOAE phase under these conditions are indeed an interesting area for future research, and we plan to explore this to determine if any significant effects are present.

William Salloom: Hi Afagh and team, very interesting study! I also have a few comments/questions on your work. My first question is in regards to the modulation function frequencies (103 and 303 Hz) used for the target signal. From your preliminary results, it appears that the largest EFR modulation enhancement occurred for the 103 Hz target compared to the 303 Hz target (Fig 3). Then, this results in a large effect on the TEOAE response around 2 kHz (Fig 5), which may be due to the increased IC input from what the manuscript details. If this IC enhanced response from a modulated sound results in increased gain reduction, do you think that these types of experiments may be replicated in human OAE experiments? There had been a controversial finding in the human OAE literature where modulated MOCR elicitors (100 Hz) had differential effects compared to non-modulated MOCR elicitors (Maison et al. *Neuroscience*. 91(1) (1999), Pages 133-138). However, other studies found no-effect of modulation frequency (100 Hz) on MOCR elicitors and gain reduction (Backus. Thesis MIT. (2005); Boothalingam et al. *Neuroscience Letters*. 580 (2014), Pages 56-61). Could it be that the 100 Hz modulation frequency is not within the best range of sensitivity to humans in those studies? I am wondering if you (or lab) has thought about doing a psychoacoustic component to this line of research including AM detection task with your chinchillas? It would be interesting to see if the normal hearing chinchillas perform differently in AM detection compared to chinchillas exposed to carboplatin. Since the EFR data is showing a difference in enhancement between these two groups of chinchillas, then perhaps you may find a similar result manifested in a psychoacoustic task (at least with a 103 Hz signal, and not the 303 Hz signal). Looking forward to how your study progresses!

Afagh Farhadi: Thank you for your insightful comments and feedback. Backus (2005, MIT Thesis) observed enhancement at 100 Hz in one subject, similar to the findings of Maison et al. (1999, *Neuroscience*, 91(1)). However, this was not the case for other subjects. The variability across different studies might suggest individual or species-specific differences in both IC and MOC modulation transfer functions (MTF). Differences in experimental procedures, stimulus design, and analysis methods could explain the discrepancies observed across studies. Additionally, even an unmodulated noise (as we observe in this study) itself can strongly activate the IC due to its inherent fluctuations, hence changes in AM noise modulation frequency might be less significant if the MOC effect is saturated. For the SAM tone used in this study, if the modulation frequency is out of range, it likely does not activate the IC (as we observed in model responses). Regarding the psychoacoustic question, our lab has conducted behavioral studies that demonstrate chinchillas can perform AM detection tasks. Chinchillas in fact demonstrated much superior performance compared to rabbits, and their thresholds is comparable to performance of budgerigars (Carney et al., 2013; Henry et al., 2016) and humans. Although we don't have data on carboplatin-exposed chinchillas, our preliminary results with temporary threshold shifts (TTS) from mild noise exposure show a small effect (1-2 dB) on threshold levels. Investigating behavioral thresholds in carboplatin-exposed chinchillas would be an interesting future direction to further explore these findings.